

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EFFECT OF LPS ON CAPSULAR ELEMENTS OF SPINAL GANGLIA AND PERIPHERAL NERVE. COMPARATIVE STUDY ON ANIMAL MODEL

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Abstract

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) that is the primary component of the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria which used to investigate a process - inflammation in nervous system. There is comparative study on specific properties of capsule surrounding spinal ganglia (also named sensory ganglia situated on dorsal root of spinal cord) and perineurial layer of peripheral nerve (sciatic nerve). Here, we investigated the effect of LPS (endotoxin) on capsular elements, as well as on peripheral (sciatic nerve) nerve in a rat model. During experimental research, 20 rats were used. At acute endotoxemia (after 2 hours of administration of LPS) the effect of LPS on structural elements of spinal ganglia first detected feature were formation of edematous fluid, which accumulated on large amount and influenced to covering capsular elements and connective tissue investment of peripheral nerve.

Keywords: LPS, endotoxin, spinal ganglia, capsule, peripheral nerve.

Introductions. Bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS) may contribute to the manifestation of inflammatory pain within structures of the afferent somatosensory system (1). Spinal ganglia, the place where situated neuronal cell bodies that give rise to peripheral nociceptive nerve endings. The latter detected different stimuli (pain, mechanical, chemical, thermal and else) and by neurons of spinal ganglia information is forwarded to the central nervous system. Sensory spinal ganglia represent transfer stations between somatosensory signals from the periphery to the brain. Therefore investigation on spinal ganglia useful approaches to combat some of the pathophysiological lesion during inflammation. In this context, we focused LPS-induced effects on covering connective tissue elements of spinal ganglia (capsule) and peripheral nerve.

Aim of research was to comparative study of effect LPS on capsular elements of spinal ganglia and on connective tissue elements of peripheral nerve.

Materials and methods. The material of investigation had been dorsal root ganglia and peripheral (sciatic) nerves were purchased from 20 adult white rats with a weight of 200-220 grams. The all procedures on animals complied with the Principles of Laboratory and Animal Care mounted by the Azerbaijan Medical University. The animals had been bred on pathogen free special a standard laboratory condition. Research rats were divided into 2 groups: control and experimental. In control group into the tail vein of animals was ad-

ministered 0,5 ml physiological salt solution. In experimental groups of animals acute experimental endotoxemia was caused by intravenous administration of LPS from E. coli (Serotype 0111: B4 InvivoGen, San Diego, CA 92121) at a dose of 1,0 mg/kg dissolved in saline. After 2 hours of the intravenous injection the animals decapitated under ketamine anesthesia; the abdominal and thoracic cavity of the rats opened, then was taken out the internal organs and the vertebral bodies were cut. Later by the help of special lancet, a spinal canal opened and spinal ganglions, corresponding nerve and sciatic nerve were removed from the soft tissue in intervertebral foramen level. The all (from both groups) specimens were fixed in a solution containing paraformaldehyde 2%, glutaraldehyde 2%, picric acid 0,1% and a buffer phosphate solution at a pH of 7.4; later postfixated with a solution of 1% osmium tetroxide in 2 hours; at last prepared into Spurr and Araldit-Epon blocks. Obtained thin (0,5 µm thick) and semithin (1-2µm) section were dyed with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsine (2), afterwards observed by Latimet (Leitz) microscope. Ultrathin section, 70-80 nanometers thick, were cut from the same blocks on ultratome (LKB -III, Leica EM UC7) and treated with 2% acetate of uranyl solution, as well as 0,6% lead citrate solution (3). After examining of ultrathin sections under 80-120 kV in transmission electron microscope JEM-1400 (Jeol, Japan) taken the electronograms.

Results and discussions. The connective tissue surrounding spinal sensory ganglia known as capsule of

ganglia. Capsule, that regulating homeostasis within organ, isolated ganglion from external environment, as well as composed of outer (epineurium) and inner (perineurium) layer. The composition (fibers, cells) of cap-

sule clearly visible under electron microscope. On figure 1 seen comparison of capsular elements of spinal ganglia with covering connective tissue investment of sciatic nerve.

Figure 1. Comparative electronograms of spinal ganglia capsule (A) and connective tissue investment of sciatic nerve (B). TEM. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: uranyl acetate and lead citrate.

Magnification: A 25000 times, B 20000 times. Abbreviation: Epi-epineurium, Per-perineurium, End-endoneurium, PC-perineurial cells, BCF 1–bundle of collagen type 1 fibers, BCF 3–bundle of collagen type 3 fibers, MNF – myelinated nerve fibers.

On electronograms (Fig. 1) shows the cellular and fibrillary elements involving in composition of capsule and connective tissue investment of the sciatic nerve. The capsule of spinal ganglia composed of epineurium, perineurium and endoneurium (fig. 1A). As the same composition are present in sciatic nerve wrapped connective tissue elements. However, the thickness of epineurial layer of sciatic nerve extremely outstanding the same layer of capsule, but perineurium of capsule thicker than in sciatic nerve. Perineurium in both structure (on electronogram) contains perineurial cells, which arranged in 6-7 layer in capsule, also 4-5 layer in sciatic nerve. Within endoneurium visible myelinated nerve fibers in sciatic nerve (fig. 1B). Apparently, within perineurium - between the perineurial cells (located in the inner layer of the capsule), also in the epi- and endoneurium detected mainly bundles of collagen fibers (indicated by stars). It should be noted that the collagen fibers, located in the endoneurium of sciatic

nerve and between perineurial cells of capsule of spinal ganglia are composed of thin reticular fibers, mainly of type III collagen fibrils. Ultrastructurally, the fact approved that because of the reticular fibers are thinner than the fibers located in the epineurial layer.

The epineurial layer of both the capsule and the sciatic nerves, unlike the endoneurium and perineurium, are composed of dense bundles of collagen fibers formed mainly from type I collagen fibrils, which are resistant to mechanical effects. The fact that the bundles of collagen fibers involved in the organization of epineurial membranes have a compatible structure with each other (the ganglion and sciatic nerve), there is a sharp difference is clearly visible between their morphometric parameters in thickness of layer. The results of the conducted morphometric studies show that nerve bundles with the largest diameter are at least two times less than the diameter of the spinal ganglia, the thickness of the epineurial membrane surrounding them from

the outside is at least 4-5 times greater than the thickness of the epineural membrane of the ganglia capsule (fig.1).

As a result of the effect of LPS on structural elements of spinal ganglia first detected edematous fluid, which in large amount situated around ganglia (indicated by double arrow on fig.2A), under capsular and intraganglionic regions (marked by red star on fig.2C) under light microscope. The structural components of spinal ganglia such as connective tissue element – capsule (shown on Fig.2A, C), extra and

intra ganglionic vessels and nerve elements (neuron, glial cells and nerve fibers) are also exposed to various degrees of deformation, which gives reason to conclude that the amount of the formed edematous fluid is an enormous amount high. On this research we focused on alteration that detected on capsular elements of spinal ganglia. The analysis of the obtained materials shows that the large size of the “perineural windows” (PW) (shown on Fig.2A, 2b by single arrow) revealed during acute endotoxemia in the capsule of spinal ganglia.

Fig. 2. Microscopic slides of changes in capsular elements of spinal ganglion (A, C) and peripheral nerve, nerve bundles (B, D) during acute endotoxemia. Semithin section. The explanation is given in the text. Stain: methylene blue. Scale bar: A 200 µm, B 100 µm, C, D 50 µm. Abbreviation: Cp capsule, SSG sensory spinal ganglia, NF nerve fibers, PSN primary sensory neuron.

As well as the coming into being the PW in capsule of spinal ganglia, that occupy most of the field of view even under the small magnifications of a light microscope. Also at acute endotoxemia, the PW observed in nerve bundles with an average diameter of 400-600 μm , which participate in the organization of peripheral nerves (fig. 2B, 2D). However the size of latter are much smaller than the previous. The large sized PW on capsule of spinal ganglia can be explained by the following facts:

a) the density of intra and extraganglionic vessels network is more high than peripheral nerve (4); the perimeter of the luminal surface of the vessels of ganglia (the size of the exchange surface) is at least 1.8 times more than the perimeter of the spinal ganglia's capsule, the corresponding indicator is at least two times less in the sciatic nerve bundles (it means the luminal surface of the vessels of peripheral nerve less than perimeter of the nerve bundle);

b) while the diameter of the largest bundles involving in the organization of peripheral nerves does not exceed 600 μm , this indicator is at least twice as large in spinal ganglia;

c) the thickness of the epineural layer of the spinal ganglia's capsule is at least three times thinner than the thickness of the corresponding layer of the sciatic nerves.

Conclusion. The formed large amount edema destructed the structural elements of spinal ganglia, especially its capsule, that the selective permeability functions of the connective tissue elements surrounding the spinal ganglia along with the vessels are completely disrupted. It should be noted that the density of vessels

network within organ, the size of the exchange surface of its vessels and thickness of surrounding connective tissue elements directly influenced to amount of edematous fluid at acute endotoxemia.

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